

Japanese Figures in the Video Game Industry: Shinji Mikami

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Today I will talk about Shinji Mikami, another renowned Japanese professional associated with the video game industry. Widely known for giving rise to the survival horror genre as we know it today—a variant of pure horror video games—he has been a key figure for the company where he achieved his earliest successes: Capcom.

Early years and his beginnings at Capcom

Shinji Mikami was born in August 1965 in Iwakuni, a city in Yamaguchi Prefecture, Japan. He obtained his degree from the Faculty of Commerce at Doshisha University, specialising in marketing. In Japan, students are often invited to attend company presentations so that firms can identify potential recruits. Mikami attended several of these presentations, and it was Capcom's that attracted his attention the most.

Having played very few video games until then—he has mentioned on occasion that the first game he ever played was a professional wrestling title in an arcade—the company nonetheless sparked his interest in working in the industry. Capcom initially rejected his application, but, rather mysteriously, a week after receiving this refusal they called him back and offered him a position.

His first project at Capcom was *Capcom Quiz: Hatena? no Daibōken* in 1990—a quiz game related to the company's video games, released for Nintendo's Game Boy handheld console—. As we shall see, Mikami did not always work on horror games—indeed, when he was young he had not even intended to develop video games at all.

Mikami had always wanted to become a Formula One driver. He even worked on a cancelled video game based on the high-speed sport, which had been planned for the Game Boy.

Until 1993, he worked on three Disney titles: *Who Framed Roger Rabbit?* for Game Boy, and *Goof Troop* and *Aladdin* for the Super Nintendo. The latter was a commercial success, selling nearly two million copies —an impressive figure for the time—. After *Aladdin*, the company approached him and offered him a promotion —until then he had been a “junior” designer.

Left: a screenshot from *Aladdin* (1993). Right: *The Night of the Living Dead* (1968), directed by George Andrew Romero. This film was one of Mikami’s greatest creative influences. It also shows that he was a resourceful creator, as the theme of a Disney video game had very little to do with the world of the living dead.

From a young age, Shinji was fascinated by horror cinema, being a follower of George Andrew Romero’s horror films and other very popular titles during his youth, such as *The Texas Chain Saw Massacre*. At the same time, however, he often felt frustrated, believing that cinema limited its characters. He experienced the familiar reaction many of us have when watching a horror film: questioning the outcome, the actions taken by the protagonists, and the events that happen to them, often thinking that, in certain situations, they should act differently.

He wanted to bring these ideas into the world of video games. His aim was for video games to allow players to make the decisions that the protagonists or secondary characters of those films could not —or did not know how to— make. He always believed that this was the step video games could take to surpass cinema in certain respects. As we shall see, through his work he managed to achieve this shift to some degree.

Although Mikami has worked on many different kinds of video games, it is the horror genre for which the Japanese creator is best known worldwide. His first step into that genre came thanks to a colleague at Capcom.

It was Tokurō Fujiwara himself —director of the 1989 NES horror game *Sweet Home*— who approached Mikami in 1993 and asked him to create a new horror game franchise inspired by his own title.

Mikami’s rise in the video game industry

The approach taken by this new game, *Biohazard (Resident Evil)*, would be very different from what could be seen in other horror titles such as *Clock Tower*, which was released a few months before *Resident Evil*.

In *Clock Tower*, the environment is explored at a slower, more methodical pace, whereas in *Resident Evil* players must either flee from enemies or use violence against them, rather than simply immersing themselves in a horror adventure centred on solving puzzles —although puzzles also appear in *Resident Evil*— and using the environment to hide and escape.

Released in 1996, first for Sony’s PlayStation and later for the Sega Saturn, it was the first video game to be described as belonging to the “survival horror” genre. It was one of the early PlayStation titles and, at the same time, one of the most famous, launching Shinji Mikami to prominence because of his involvement in the project. After his work on the game, Mikami was promoted to producer and became responsible for supervising the following instalments of the franchise.

Capcom decided to support Mikami by allowing him to establish his own studio within the company. This materialised in 1999 with the creation of Capcom Production Studio 4, a team that focused on projects related to horror or survival horror games.

On several occasions, Mikami delegated the role of director on his games to Hideki Kamiya, who had worked with him since the first *Resident Evil*. Kamiya’s team was developing the next *Resident Evil* instalment, but they introduced so many new ideas that they ultimately chose to create a completely new franchise instead: *Devil May Cry* —a series of games centred on fast-paced action in the style of the *beat ’em up* genre.

Shinji Mikami himself oversaw the development of *Resident Evil – Code: Veronica*, the first *Resident Evil* game to abandon pre-rendered backgrounds in favour of fully three-dimensional environments.

Mikami’s growing reputation at the time was not based solely on his work on *Resident Evil*. He was also behind the excellent *Dino Crisis*, which transferred the narrative tension of horror to creatures already well known to fans of the Jurassic Park franchise: dinosaurs. The first instalment was developed with his team in 1999, while the sequel —developed by Capcom Production Studio 4 without Mikami directly involved— was released in 2000.

Left: *Resident Evil: Director’s Cut* (1997) for PlayStation. Right: *Dino Crisis* (1999), also released for PlayStation.

It was a much more aggressive and action-oriented game than *Resident Evil*, and players had to take into account aspects such as the fact that dinosaurs could track their scent in order to find them. While it shared many elements with the original *Resident Evil* —the protagonist, Regina, arrives at a supposedly abandoned facility in search of Dr Kirk, who had been presumed dead, only to discover the place infested with enemies; a clear parallel with the plot of the original *Resident Evil*, where the protagonists arrive at the Spencer Mansion—.

We can also see that Mikami did not always attach himself to horror projects, as demonstrated by his involvement in titles such as the visual novel series *Phoenix Wright: Ace Attorney*, for which he served as executive producer of the original trilogy, released between 2001 and 2003 for the Game Boy Advance —and later ported to other consoles—.

The games were directed by Shū Takumi. Mikami had previously worked with him on *Resident Evil 2* and *Dino Crisis*, and gave him complete creative freedom to develop whatever kind of game he wished. Takumi's passion for mystery and investigative cinema ultimately inspired the creation of the *Phoenix Wright* series.

Players assist Phoenix Wright, a novice defence attorney, in winning his cases. They can investigate the incidents in which Wright's clients are involved and must ultimately secure a “not guilty” verdict during the trials by responding to questions from the judge and the prosecutor, examining the testimonies and reactions of witnesses, and analysing evidence and crime scenes. The franchise has also been highly successful and has even received adaptations into manga, anime, and live-action film.

Mikami also produced the title *Steel Battalion*, released for the Xbox in 2002. The game required a specially designed controller —featuring around forty different buttons, for example— and, according to its co-producer Atsushi Inaba —whose ideas often align with Mikami's interest in creating new concepts in video games— it aimed to provide a level of immersion that could only truly be experienced through a video game.

Taking advantage of the superior power of the Xbox compared with other consoles of its generation, the development team set themselves the challenge of making the piloting of a “mecha” —as mechanised vehicles of various designs, including giant drivable robots, are commonly called in Japan— feel as realistic as possible for the player. You can watch the game in action by following this link.

Mikami also served as an adviser on the game *Onimusha: Warlords*, released for the PlayStation 2 in 2001, part of a well-known action game franchise that took advantage of the console's hardware capabilities to feature a soundtrack performed with real instruments —rather than the lightweight synthesised music formats common at the time— recorded with a full orchestra. The game also featured the work of the actor Takeshi Kaneshiro, who at that time was not yet widely known in the West; he provided both the voice and likeness of the protagonist. In later instalments of the series, even well-known Western actors such as Jean Reno would appear.

Left: promotional image from the *Phoenix Wright* animated series (2016). Right: Takeshi Kaneshiro as Samanosuke in *Onimusha: Warlords* (2001).

Onimusha is one of the franchises that helped popularise the highly cinematic, blockbuster-style presentation in video games that has since become so firmly established.

Final projects at Capcom

Following this, Mikami signed an agreement with Nintendo so that three Resident Evil titles would appear on the company's then current-generation console, the GameCube.

The agreement between Capcom and Nintendo also included five original games for the Nintendo GameCube, with the aim of boosting the console's sales and demonstrating strong third-party support—that is, companies developing games for hardware produced by another company, in this case Nintendo. Capcom referred to these titles as the “Capcom Five”. They were *P.N.03*, *Viewtiful Joe*, *Killer7*, *Dead Phoenix*, and *Resident Evil 4*. Of all these titles, only *P.N.03* ultimately remained exclusive to Nintendo's system.

Dead Phoenix was an action game project that was eventually cancelled. Meanwhile, *P.N.03*, although not a poor third-person shooter, failed to achieve the expected success either critically or commercially.

Killer7 was a project created by Gōichi Suda—the Japanese developer better known as Suda51—a rail shooter—that is, a game in which the character follows a predetermined path, giving the player limited or no control over movement through the environment—with a very distinctive visual style. Despite its originality, it also struggled to achieve strong sales or the level of critical acclaim that had been anticipated.

Viewtiful Joe—developed by Hideki Kamiya and supervised by Mikami—is a side-scrolling action game in the classic *beat 'em up* style of the 1980s and 1990s. It pays homage both to American superhero culture and to the Japanese *tokusatsu* genre—a term used in Japan for live-action productions that rely heavily on special effects. The game achieved moderate success—given its relatively small budget, its sales were considered sufficient to justify its development—and the franchise continued with additional titles. Joe's adventures have appeared on several consoles and even inspired an anime series.

Within the Resident Evil franchise, in addition to the well-known remake of the original game, there followed *Resident Evil Zero* and *Resident Evil 4*. The remake was very well received, while *Zero* also sold reasonably well and was generally well regarded within the industry, although not quite to the level Capcom and Mikami had hoped. As a result, there were concerns that *Resident Evil 4* might not perform well in the market. This uncertainty contributed to Mikami's decision to devote all his efforts to the development of *Resident Evil 4*.

Despite the nervousness among its developers, the game achieved great success and remains, even today, one of the most beloved entries in the series, despite differing greatly from the mechanics of the original title. It even received a remake in 2023, following the precedent set by remakes of the first three original Resident Evil games over the years—the first of which appeared in 2002, with Mikami himself involved in the development team—.

For many fans, the perceived “flaw” of *Resident Evil 4* can be understood by examining Mikami's creative philosophy. Since his earliest work as a developer and producer, he has insisted that he is not fond of endlessly prolonged series or of repeating the same experience. Instead, he favours experimentation, creativity, novelty, and the reinvention of established ideas.

For this reason, he sought to change the direction of *Resident Evil 4*—a shift that Capcom would later exaggerate and, in the eyes of many fans, distort—in order to bring freshness to the franchise. If we look closely, Mikami directed the first *Resident Evil*, but not the second or third instalments. A similar situation occurred with *Dino Crisis*: he directed the first game but delegated later entries to his team.

He returned to direct *Resident Evil 4* because he felt he had something new to contribute and wanted to make the game distinct from the rest. In fact, this title marked a turning point not only for the series but also for several other video game genres. While Mikami played a major role in redirecting the franchise, it is important to note that his intention was not necessarily to maintain this new direction permanently, but rather to create something different. In various interviews, he has described this approach as representing different phases of a story, each with its own rhythm.

The now widely popular over-the-shoulder camera was one of Mikami's key design choices for *Resident Evil 4*. The aiming system used by the characters—the control method—was also pioneering for its time. Mikami aimed to provide controls that were intuitive and easy to use, ensuring that the difficulty of his games arose not from awkward mechanics caused by technical limitations, but from well-designed enemies and carefully constructed levels.

Left: *Resident Evil 4* in its 2014 HD (“High Definition”) version. Right: *Gears of War 4* for Xbox One, released in October 2016. We can see that eleven years after the original *Resident Evil 4* (2005) —and nine years after the HD version— the influence of Mikami’s game on the gameplay of modern action and third-person shooter titles is very clear.

Even the aiming system —raising the weapon, focusing the camera on enemies, carefully adjusting one’s aim, and so on— later became widely adopted in third-person action games. Today these features are largely taken for granted as almost standard mechanics in third-person shooters, all derived from ideas introduced by Mikami and his team. The shift from third-person perspective to an over-the-shoulder or more focused aiming view is a mechanic that can still be seen in contemporary titles such as *Helldivers 2* (2024).

Mikami also participated as a designer on *Resident Evil: Outbreak*, the first title in the series to place a strong emphasis on cooperative and online play, an aspect that Capcom would later continue to develop in several Resident Evil instalments in which Mikami was no longer involved after leaving the company.

Clover Studio and Shinji Mikami in the present day

Following the great success of *Resident Evil 4*, Mikami founded Clover Studio within Capcom itself, together with other prominent Capcom figures such as Atsushi Inaba. Clover Studio was responsible for the ports —adaptations— of *Viewtiful Joe* to platforms other than the GameCube. Capcom had the idea of transforming the development team behind the original *Viewtiful Joe* into a larger studio capable of creating new intellectual properties, while also facilitating the development of *Viewtiful Joe 2* (2004).

The studio also developed the acclaimed game *Ōkami*, a title that combined various elements of Japanese mythology and featured the goddess Amaterasu as its protagonist, appearing in the form of a white wolf. Finally, they created *God Hand*, a *beat 'em up* for PlayStation 2 released in 2006 that paid homage both to the classic games of the genre from the 1980s and 1990s and to elements of Japanese and American popular culture.

Clover was eventually dissolved, and most members of its development and programming team were offered the opportunity to reintegrate into Capcom. However, important figures such as Shinji Mikami, Atsushi Inaba, Keiji Inafune —a designer known for his work on the Mega Man franchise—, Yoshiki Okamoto —one of the key figures behind *Street Fighter II* and *Final Fight*—, and Hideki Kamiya gradually left Capcom with the intention of establishing their own studios outside the company.

Although Clover Studio had originally been created to develop new intellectual properties in the video game industry —something Mikami had long advocated— Capcom ultimately decided to dissolve it because it did not achieve the financial success the company had hoped for. Many of the creatives who left the studio attributed their departure to what they described as rigid corporate control within Capcom and a lack of space for greater creativity and new ideas in game development.

Mikami would later recall this situation when speaking in 2015 about another famous developer, Hideo Kojima, and his situation at Konami. Former Capcom figures such as the designer Keiji Inafune, along with developers from Konami —such as Kōji Igarashi, about whom I wrote in a previous article— also left their companies or took advantage of their departure to pursue their own projects with greater creative freedom.

Some members of Clover founded Seeds Inc., which was later absorbed by ODD to create the studio PlatinumGames. Inaba, the director of *Ōkami*, joined Ignition Entertainment. Mikami, meanwhile, joined ZeniMax Media —the parent company of major game studios such as Bethesda Softworks and id Software, and itself responsible for titles such as *The Elder Scrolls Online: Tamriel Unlimited*— after ZeniMax acquired his new studio, Tangoameworks.

After leaving Clover Studio, Mikami secretly established a small studio of his own called Straight Story, which collaborated with PlatinumGames together with some of his former colleagues. Following the development of *Vanquish* in 2010 —a notable action and shooting game that was somewhat overlooked by the press and critics due to its perceived repetitiveness, the limited depth of its story, and its relatively short length, despite offering an intense display of speed, action, and excellent controls— Mikami dissolved Straight Story and founded the aforementioned studio: Tangoameworks.

Left: *God Hand* for PlayStation 2, released in 2006. Right: *Vanquish* (2010), for PlayStation 3 and Xbox 360.

Platinum Games also developed —although Mikami did not participate in them— *Bayonetta*, *Infinite Space*, and *MadWorld*, and more recently, *Bayonetta 2* for Wii U and Switch, and *Bayonetta 3* for Switch, —these last two thanks to Nintendo's support—; as well as other major titles such as *NieR: Automata*, directed by Yokō Tarō.

The cooperative relationship between Shinji Mikami and Gōichi Suda has also continued over the years, with whom he worked for his studio —Grasshopper Manufacture— on the development of *Shadows of the Damned* (2011).

The latest game directed by Shinji Mikami has been *The Evil Within* —or *Psycho Break* in Japan, “サイコブレイク”—. Furthermore, he intended to retire from the industry as a director after completing this game, continuing only as a producer, designer, or advisor, as he has done for *The Evil Within 2* (2017), *Ghostwire: Tokyo* (2020), and *Hi-Fi Rush* (2023), where he acted as executive producer.

Released for multiple gaming platforms in 2014, Mikami wanted to return to the survival horror genre with *The Evil Within*, as it had been done nearly two decades earlier under his direction or production. The director himself was very disappointed that the majority of survival horror titles were sold as such but were merely action-horror games, so he sought to satisfy fans of the genre associated with him through *The Evil Within*.

Stealth plays a more prominent role than action, and Quick Time Events —a mechanic, already present in some video games of the 80s, which consists on events requiring the rapid pressing of one or more buttons as instructions appear on screen to progress through certain sections or scenes— are not emphasised in *The Evil Within* (these events had existed since the 1980s; they are very popular today, and Mikami introduced them in *Resident Evil 4*, without expecting them to be so overused later).

Players control the investigator Sebastian Castellanos, who, while investigating incidents at a psychiatric hospital, loses consciousness when attacked and finds himself transported to a terrifying world in which the evil Ruvik controls the terrain and determines what our protagonist will encounter.

This game forces players to face various types of traps throughout the environments — drawn from a world of nightmares and madness, in the purest style of 20th-century classic horror cinema—, a world that changes according to both the game’s scripted events and the player’s actions. The experience is complemented by enemies against whom it is sometimes preferable to flee, the intelligent use and management of available items and ammunition, and the sense that, despite a scripted storyline, players can still be surprised.

Following the release of *The Evil Within*, its downloadable content (DLC) added further gameplay minutes, allowing players to experience the adventure from other characters’ perspectives.

For years, it was known that Shinji Mikami and his team were working on new projects, already mentioned earlier, in which he participated as executive producer. It is also known that he intends to revisit the concepts of the *Dino Crisis* and *God Hand* franchises, potentially releasing new entries in the future, after several *Dino Crisis* projects were cancelled over the years, and strong rumours in early 2026 suggest a remake or reboot of the franchise.

Sebastian fleeing from a chainsaw-wielding sadist in *The Evil Within*. The game was released for Xbox 360, Xbox One, Playstation 3, Playstation 4, and PC.

Sources

- **Texts consulted from:** Capcom, Mobygames, IGN, Platinum Games, Tango Gameworks | **Text created by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es]
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